

and yield. At harvest, rice had a significant plant height reduction of 9-12% and tiller number reduction of 18-24%. The pure stand of upland rice yielded 2.8 t/ha; intercropped rice showed significant yield reduction. Reduced plant height, tiller number, and grain yield was correlated positively with

Lamtoro cumulative dry weight.

The results suggest a negative interaction between Lamtoro cultivars and intercropped upland rice with the 2 m row spacing. Row spacing should be adjusted for optimum rice yield.

A decrease in exchangeable A1+H and A1 saturation and an increase in

exchangeable Ca+Mg occurred in the intercropped plots. Intercropping upland rice and Lamtoro and returning Lamtoro biomass to the soil over a period of several years may actually result in decreased A1 and increased plant nutrients in the soil. □

Cumulative dry weight of Lamtoro after 3 cuttings, growth and yield of intercropped upland rice, and soil chemical properties after rice harvest.^a Sumatra, Indonesia, 1983-84.

Lamtoro variety	Cumulative dry weight (t/ha)	Upland rice plant height (cm)			Upland rice tillers (no./hill)			Upland rice grain yield (t/ha)	Exchangeable A1+H (meq/100 g)	Exchangeable Ca+Mg (meq/100 g)	A1 saturation (%)
		30 DAS	60 DAS	Harvest	30 DAS	60 DAS	Harvest				
Peru	4.6 a	43 a	73 a	111 c	19 a	34 a	13 b	2.1 b	3.9 ab	0.8 a	82 ab
K-8	5.2 a	45 a	74 a	120 ab	20 a	37 a	14 b	2.4 b	3.8 ab	0.8 a	82 ab
K-28	6.3 a	47 a	76 a	120 ab	18 a	38 a	14 b	1.7 c	2.8 b	1.5 b	63 b
Gung	4.7 a	41 a	69 a	115 bc	17 a	39 a	14 b	2.1 b	3.5 ab	0.9 a	84 a
Control	-	42 a	79 a	126 a	21 a	36 a	17 a	2.8 a	4.0 a	0.7 a	85 a

^aDAS = days after seeding. Data are means of 4 replications. Mean separation by DMRT at 5%.

Performance of transplanted aman rice varieties in cropping pattern trials

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We evaluated six T. aman rice varieties in cropping pattern trials in the 1982-1983 late wet seasons. The Hathazari cropping systems site is medium high land. The objective was to identify short-duration varieties with higher yields at low fertilizer levels in the broadcast aus - T. aman - cowpea cropping pattern under rainfed conditions.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with five replications across farms. Each year, 37-d-old seedlings were transplanted 24-27 Aug at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 60-17.6-16.6 kg NPK/ha.

The varieties exhibited significant variations in yield, days to flowering, and days to maturity (see table).

BR11 is resistant to lodging and shattering, with medium grains. Its market value is higher because its grains produce quality rice and pop. □

Performance of T. aman varieties in farmers' cropping patterns at Hathazari, Bangladesh, 1982-83.^a

Variety	Flowering (DT)		Maturity (DT)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1982	1983	1982	1983	1982	1983
BR3	68 b	70 ab	109 b	112 b	3.2 a	3.5 ab
BR4	65 c	67 bc	106 bc	109 bc	2.6 ab	3.0 b
BR10	64 c	66 c	106 bc	108 c	3.2 a	3.4 b
BR11	62 d	64 c	101 c	108 c	3.2 a	4.3 a
Pajam	56 e	59 d	97 d	101 d	2.8 a	2.7 b
Chakkal (check)	72 a	73 a	114 a	117 a	2.0 b	2.8 b
CV (%)	2.7	4.6	2.9	2.1	19.8	20.0

^aDT = days after transplanting.

SOCIOECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

Production

Economics of rice gall midge (GM) management in resistant and susceptible cultures

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We studied the incidence of GM in three resistant and one GM-susceptible cultivars with and without pest management in a split-plot design with three replications during the 1986 wet season.

GM incidence in the susceptible variety crossed the economic threshold (ETL) 48 d after transplanting (DT)